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Impact of Artisanal Refining on Soil and Human Health: A Case Study of Oyigba Community, River State, Nigeria

**Bridget E. Diagi^{1,*}, Martin Iwuji¹, Deborah O. Diagi³, Oliver Uchechi¹,
Susan I. Ajiere², David O. Edokpa⁴**

¹ Department of Environmental Management, School of Environmental Sciences,
Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

² Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Port-Harcourt,
Choba, Port-Harcourt, Nigeria

³ Department of Chemical Engineering, Covenant University, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria

⁴ Department of Geography and Environment, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

*E-mail address: edeoli@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The Niger Delta region of Nigeria, distinguished for its ecological diversity, faces serious environmental degradation as a result of artisanal oil refining. This study evaluates the impact of these activities on soil quality, human health and environment in Oyigba community, Rivers State. Soil samples were collected using soil auger from three impacted locations. A total of 12(twelve) samples were collected with sampling depth of 0-15 cm, 15-30 cm and 30-45 cm. Parameters analyzed include pH, Lead, Cadmium, Mercury and Arsenic. A well-structured questionnaire was used to collect information on the impact of artisanal refining on health of the community. Findings shows notable soil contamination, with lead and cadmium concentration reaching 1.483 mg/kg and 0.061 mg/kg, respectively, however pH value dropped to 6.24 indicating increased acidity. Community health assessment indicates high occurrence of respiratory issues represented by 91.8%, skin irritation with 91.8%, and fatigue represented with 65.6%, associated with long-term exposure to hydrocarbon pollutants. In like manner, 83.6% of the respondents reported a reduction in farmland productivity in the area, while 88.5% detected reduced crop yields. Similarly, the respondents signify that cassava with 65.6%, cocoyam with 54.1% and corn with 32.8% were the crops mostly affected by the activities, emphasizing concern on food security in that region. Majority of the respondents 75.4% perceived the

overall impact of artisanal refining as negative. This study emphasized the immediate need and attention of regulatory agencies to reduce environmental and health risk linked with artisanal refining by being proactive and ensuring adequate monitoring of vulnerable communities. Policy recommendation includes the restoration of degraded lands, and a sustainable development plan to protect affected populations and restore ecological stability in the community.

Keywords: Artisanal refining, soil pollution, impact, human health, River State

1. INTRODUCTION

Niger Delta region is recognized globally for its ecological richness and biodiversity as well as its wealth from natural resources such as crude oil. The ecosystem in the Niger Delta region has good biodiversity that supports the growth of plants and animals, good land that supports variety of crops, resourceful tree and different species of fishes (Donwa et al., 2015; Ite et al., 2013). Ever since the discovery of crude oil in 1956, Nigeria and indeed the Niger Delta region has faced economic losses as a result of pollution, corruption, and neglect of basic infrastructure. This neglect on the one hand, has led to a lot of illegal activities connected to crude oil. Amongst these illegal activities is the illegal refining of stolen crude or what is popularly known in the region as artisanal refining or “Kpo fire” which has resulted to a lot of degradation and health related illness within the region. These illegal activities have resulted in pollution problems that have devastating effects (Dominic, 2016; Elenwo & Urho, 2017) such that the water, land and even air in this region is largely polluted (Coderoni & Perito, 2020).

Similarly, incidences of pollution related to health challenges have heightened in the region as both surface and underground water sources suffer pollution from these activities resulting to severe poisoning of water (Bebeteidoh, Pazouki, & Norman, 2020; Beshiru, Okareh, Chigor, & Igbiosa, 2018) and have escalated environmental deterioration, health challenges as well as social and economic issues of recent (Ikezam et al., 2021). One of the greatest problems with artisanal refining is the fact that their operation is done without adherence to environmental regulation and this has led to severe contamination of soil due to the high concentration of hydrocarbon and heavy metals resulting in massive loss of productive farm lands within the region (Richard et al., 2022; Ejiba et al., 2016). It involves the extraction of crude oil using rudimentary and hazardous methods, which results to environmental degradation, health risk and social unrest (Hart, 2024).

The effect of artisanal refining such as oil spills and waste discharge, pollution goes beyond the destruction of farmland as it also affects aquatic environment disrupting their water chemistry which could result in biodiversity decline or extinction biodiversity (Amadi & Nworgu, 2023; Onuh et al., 2021). As a result of the crude methods used in artisanal refining, waste from the operations is dumped on nearby lands, streams and river which has resulted in serious impact to the environment and people’s health. Consequently, the activities of artisanal refining expose the community to severe air pollution such as soot and toxic gases that can bring about respiratory problems, cause cancer and dysfunctional growth (Onuh et al., 2021; Richard et al., 2023). Hazardous waste introduced in the environment affect the physical and chemical properties of the soil (Raimi et al., 2022). its presence in the soil becomes a threat to ground water thereby contaminating and making the water unfit for ingestion bringing about safety concern on portable water sources in the region (Izah et al., 2022; 2016; Ogamba et al.,

2015; Agedah et al., 2015; Izah and Srivastav, 2015; Murray, 1984; Igbeneghu, 2014; Pontara, 2011; Olayemi, 1994; Alabi, 2024; Raimi et al., 2022, 2021, 2020; 2018; Gift and Raimi, 2020).

Illegal refining has led to soil contamination and pollution thereby affecting the fertility of the soil. (Richard et al, 2023) pointed out that artisanal refining affects the physiochemical and microbial composition of soil, hydrocarbons absorbed by plant as a result of the activities increased human biodiversity contamination as well as loss of farmlands, and increase soil erosion. Resulting to land, renewable resource, and agricultural degradation (Kadafe, 2012). This study therefore seeks to investigate the effects of artisanal refining on soil quality, human health and the environment.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Ahoda West Local Government Area (LGA) of Rivers State spans an area of approximately 1,621 square kilometers and is geographically located between latitude $4^{\circ}40'38''$ North and longitude $6^{\circ}25'42''$ East in the north western part of Rivers State (Rivers State Ministry of Information, 2006). It is situated northwest of Port Harcourt, with its administrative capital in the town of Akinma. The LGA comprises approximately 100 communities (National Bureau of Statistics, 2010) and had an estimated population of 249,425 in 2006, which grew to about 435,645 by 2024, according to projections by the National Population Commission (NPC, 2006; NPC, 2024).

Figure 1. Study area showing sampled locations.

The LGA comprises approximately 100 communities (National Bureau of Statistics, 2010) and had an estimated population of 249,425 in 2006, which grew to about 435,645 by 2024, according to projections by the National Population Commission (NPC, 2006; NPC, 2024). This population growth reflects an annual growth rate of 3.2%. The region experiences a tropical climate with a prominent rainy season and short dry season. The dry season is constrained to December and January, with harmattan conditions that are less pronounced compared to other parts of the area. Food crops such as plantain, rice, banana, yam, cassava, and sugarcane including cash crops such as palm oil, cocoa, and elastic which boost the economy and serves as source of income to farmers (Rivers State Ministry of Information, 2006).

Soil Sampling Techniques

A soil auger was used to collect soil samples from four different locations. Three of the samples were collected from the impacted area (Plate A, B C and D) where artisanal refining activity is conducted, and a control site with no artisanal refining activity. Twelve (12) samples were collected in total, with the sampling depths of 0-15 cm, 15-30 cm and 30-45 cm assess potential contamination. The analysis focused on the following parameters: pH, Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd), Mercury (Hg), and Arsenic (As). A pH meter was used to measure the acidity or alkalinity of the soil samples, while Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) was used to determine the concentrations of heavy metals (Pb, Cd, Hg, and As) in the soil samples.

Plates A, B, C and D. Impacted Artisanal Refining sites in the Study area.

Assessment of impact of artisanal refining on health and environment

In order to assess the impact of artisanal refining on health and environment, a structured questionnaire was designed to solicit information from the community. The calculated sample size of 367 questionnaires was divided into six family clines in oyigba community. This resulted to 61 (sixty -one) questionnaires which was distributed collectively to the six-family clan representing the entire population of the community. The 61(sixty-one) questionnaires were distributed randomly within the family clan to ensure fair representation of households, especially those residing near the artisanal refining activities. The questionnaire was designed to collect information on the following, Residents' perceptions of environmental changes (e.g., soil degradation, vegetation loss), Health impacts attributed to artisanal refining activities and Socio-economic effects, such as changes in income, farming productivity, and livelihoods.

To determine the appropriate sample size to use for the questionnaire survey, the Yaro Yamane formula (Yamane, 1967) was applied to the population of Oyigba community.

The formula is as follows:

$$\text{Sample size Determination } n = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)}$$

where: N = 4554: Total population of Oyigba community (based on the 2024 estimate derived from the 3.2% annual population growth rate from the last census conducted by the National Population Commission). e = 0.05: Margin of error (5%).

Substituting these values into the formula:

$$n = \frac{4554}{1 + 4554(0.05^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{4554}{1 + 4554(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{4554}{12.385} \approx 367$$

hence, a total of 367 was calculated to be the number of questionnaires to be used for the study.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 displays the results of laboratory analysis carried out on 12 soil samples collected from Oyigba community. It shows the pH levels of the soil and the concentration of heavy metals, including arsenic (As), lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), and mercury (Hg) across all locations including the control site. This finding provides detailed understanding into potential soil contamination in the area, with contrast made between sampled location and the control values.

Concentrations of heavy metals and other soil quality parameters

The results in Table 1 shows that the pH values across all samples reflect some degree of variability. Sample 1 demonstrated a range of 6.36 to 6.49, with slight differences between the

three locations and the control point showing a pH value of 6.48. sample 2 has a pH value ranging from 6.24 to 6.54, which is below the acceptable value for agricultural crop cultivation indicating slight acidic condition which could be attributed to contamination from these illegal activities. Sample 3 has a pH range of 6.24 to 6.44, also showing almost similar acidic condition but the control sample recorded a pH value of 6.58 which is more neutral compared to others. From the result, the pH value of the study area ranges from 6.24 to 6.58 indicating slight acidic condition. Agricultural crops do well in a soil pH that ranges from 6.0 to 7.5, which ensures optimal nutrient availability, although the observed pH values fall within the lower limit of good agricultural soils. When a soil condition is slightly acidic or neutral it is ideal for healthy plant growth and effective farming practice.

Table 1. Concentrations of heavy metals and other soil quality parameters.

PARAMETERS		pH	Arsenic, As	Cadmium, Cd	Lead, Pb	Mercury, Hg
UNIT		-	Mg/kg	Mg/kg	Mg/kg	Mg/kg
METHOD		EPA 9045D	EPA7000B			
SAMPLE ID	FIELD ID					
Sample 1	Location 1	6.36	0.007	0.049	1.483	<0.001
	Location 2	6.45	0.004	0.017	0.303	<0.001
	Location 3	6.49	<0.001	0.032	0.294	<0.001
	Control	6.29	<0.001	0.017	0.153	<0.001
Sample 2	Location 1	6.29	<0.001	0.061	0.437	<0.001
	Location 2	6.24	0.009	0.039	0.183	<0.001
	Location 3	6.54	0.007	0.048	0.281	<0.001
	Control	6.35	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Sample 3	Location 1	6.44	<0.001	0.048	0.403	<0.001
	Location 2	6.26	<0.001	0.016	0.367	<0.001
	Location 3	6.35	<0.001	0.046	0.269	<0.001
	Control	6.58	<0.001	<0.001	0.136	<0.001

Source: Author fieldwork, 2025

From Table 1 the concentration of lead in sample 1 range from 0.294mg/kg to 1.483 mg/kg across all the sampled locations. From Table 1, the highest value is detected in location 1 having a value of 1.483 mg/kg with the lowest value detected in location 3 having a value of 0.294 mg/kg. The control site had a value of 0.153 mg/kg revealing less contamination,

moreover all the values of lead in sample 1 falls below the DPR permissible limit of 85mg/kg but with continuous exposure to refining activities in the environment, the concentration of Lead is likely to increase, which is worrisome as lead is harmful to human health and prolong exposure can affect the brain, nervous system, and even cause damage to the kidney.

Cadmium concentration ranged from 0.017 mg/kg – 0.049 mg/kg, though lower than lead in all location. in sample 1, cadmium recorded high values in artisanal refining sites indicating that artisanal refining activities significantly increase cadmium content especially in location 1 and 3 having values of 0.049 mg/kg and 0.032 mg/kg respectively. The control site and location 2 recorded lowest values of 0.017 mg/kg respectively. Cadmium content falls below the DPR limit of 0.8 mg/kg.

Despite its low concentration, if exposed for a very long period of time, it can result to health issues especially in a pH condition that is slightly acidic which can lead to the mobility of the contaminant in the soil and can be absorbed by plant thereby contaminating food chain, affecting plant growth, and the consumers of the crops.

The concentration of arsenic in sample 1 differed, with its value ranging from <0.001 to 0.007 mg/kg with location 1 and 2 having the highest value of 0.007 mg/kg to 0.004 mg/kg respectively. the control site and location 3 had the lowest value of <0.001 mg/kg respectively. This shows that arsenic content in the soil has been considerably raised as a result of artisanal refining activities particularly in location 1 and 2 but still below the DPR detectable limit of 29 mg/kg, arsenic is highly mobile especially in an acidic soil and can infiltrate to ground water contaminating it and causing serious health issues like cancer, cardiovascular diseases, seizure and even reproductive and developmental issues if consumed by humans. Mercury content on the other hand, had a value of <0.001 mg/kg across all the location which is below the DPR permissible limit of 0.3 mg/kg.

On the average, the concentration of lead in sample 2 is lower than the concentration of lead in sample 1. Lead concentration in sample 2 ranged from 0.437 mg/kg – <0.001 mg/kg, lead content in location 1 has the highest value of 0.437mg/kg followed by 0.281 mg/kg in location 3 and 0.183 mg/kg in location 2 with the lowest value detected in the control site having a value of <0.001 mg/kg signifying more lead contamination in artisanal refining site, this pose serious health risk to humans, could reduce plant growth and affect agricultural production. Cadmium content in sample 2 is more than its concentration in sample 1 although ranged from 0.061-<0.001 mg/kg in sample 2 it is still below the DPR permissible limit of 0.8 mg/kg. In sample 2 cadmium has the highest concentration in location 1 with a value of 0.061 mg/kg followed by location 3 with a value of 0.048 mg/kg and location 2 with a value of 0.039 mg/kg.

The control site had the lowest value of <0.001 mg/kg signifying a non-detectable cadmium value, cadmium thrive in an acidic condition as it becomes mobile and very toxic and with the pH values in location 1 and 2 cadmium mobility will be more thereby affecting crops and human health. Arsenic content in sample 2 had values ranging from <0.001 mg/kg-0.009 mg/kg. Although arsenic concentration in sample 2 is more than its concentration in sample 1,

The highest arsenic value is detected in location 2 with a value of 0.009 mg/kg followed by its concentration in location 3 but location 1 and the control site has a non-detectable arsenic value of <0.001 mg/kg. Although still below the DPR detectable limit arsenic in an anaerobic soils like wetlands, and waterlogged areas exist as Arsenite (As^{3+}) which is very soluble and toxic and can contaminate the ground water thereby polluting it and making it unsafe for consumption and threat to aquatic organism. Mercury concentration with value of <0.001 mg/kg in all its locations signifies non-contamination.

Lead (Pb) values were generally higher than other parameters in table 1 with sample 3 higher than sample 2 but lower than sample 1. The concentration of lead in sample 3 ranged from 0.403 mg/kg – 0.136 mg/kg, with the highest value recorded in location 1 having a value of 0.403 mg/kg followed by location 2 with a value of 0.367 mg/kg and location 3 with a value of 0.269 mg/kg the control site had the lowest lead concentration of 0.136 mg/kg. The high values of lead concentration in artisanal refining site shows the increased soil pollution caused by the activities though below the DPR permissible limit of 85 mg/kg can result in lead (Pb) accumulation in the soil causing health related issues and also affecting crops and vegetation, and increasing human exposure through ingestion.

Cadmium in sample 3 has a concentration level ranging from <0.001 mg/kg – 0.048 mg/kg with location 1 and 3 having the highest value of 0.048 mg/kg and 0.046 mg/kg respectively the control site has the lowest value of <0.001 mg/kg signifying a rise of cadmium concentration in artisanal refining site although below the DPR limit cadmium can affect plant growth and bioaccumulate in crops. prolong exposure of cadmium can increase risk of kidney damage and respiratory issues. Arsenic concentration in sample 3 is <0.001 mg/kg across all its location indicating a positive condition as well as mercury with a value of <0.001 mg/kg across all its location signifying a positive condition but should be monitored regularly to ensure safety as they can be harmful to human.

Statistical Representation of the Results

The statistical analysis shows the data variability and central tendency of the result by measuring the mean, standard deviation, and standard error.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistic of soil parameters in sample 1.

Parameters	Mean (Sample 1)	Std. Dev. (Sample 1)	Std. Error (Sample 1)	Mean (Control)	Std. Dev. (Control)	Std. Error (Control)
pH	6.433333333	0.066583281	0.038441875	6.47	0.115325626	0.066583281
Arsenic	0.0037	0.003459769	0.001997498	0.0001	0	0
Cadmium	0.032666667	0.016010413	0.009243616	0.005733333	0.00975722	0.006899396
Lead	0.693333333	0.683886199	0.394841881	0.096366667	0.083801571	0.04838286
Mercury	0.0001	0	0	0.0001	0	0

Source: Authors Analysis

The result in sample 1 Table 2, shows that the mean value of arsenic concentration was 0.0037 mg/kg with standard deviation of 0.0035, and standard error of 0.0020, indicating low arsenic levels. The values were slightly increased compared to the control, which showed negligible arsenic concentrations with lower statistical values having mean of 0.0001 mg/kg, standard deviation of 0, and standard error of 0. In sample 1 the mean concentration of cadmium is 0.0327 mg/kg, with standard deviation value of 0.0160, and standard error value of 0.0092, which is significantly higher than the control, where the mean value is 0.0057 mg/kg, standard deviation value is 0.0098, and standard error value is 0.0069.

Lead has the highest concentration in sample 1 compared to other samples, with a mean value of 0.6933 mg/kg, standard deviation of 0.6839, and standard error of 0.3948, compared to the control with lower statistical value having mean of 0.0964 mg/kg, standard deviation of 0.0838, and standard error of 0.0484. The changes in lead concentration in sample 1 shows uneven contamination, likely as a result of artisanal refining activities. The concentration of mercury remains negligible in both sample 1 and the control site. The pH of soil sample 1 had a mean of 6.43, standard deviation of 0.666, and standard error of 0.0384 which is a little lower than the control pH with a mean value of 6.47, standard deviation of 0.1153, and standard error of 0.0666 showing stable and slightly acidic soil condition.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistic of soil parameters in sample 2.

Parameter	Mean (Sample 2)	Std. Dev. (Sample 2)	Std. Error (Sample 2)	Mean (Control)	Std. Dev. (Control)	Std. Error (Control)
pH	6.356666667	0.160727513	0.092796073	6.47	0.115325626	0.066583281
Arsenic	0.007	0.004669404	0.002695882	0.0001	0	0
Cadmium	0.049333333	0.01106044	0.006385748	0.005733333	0.00975722	0.006899396
Lead	0.300333333	0.12809892	0.073957946	0.096366667	0.083801571	0.04838286
Mercury	0.0001	0	0	0.0001	0	0

Source: Authors Analysis

The result in sample 2, Table 3 shows that mean value of arsenic concentration was highest among all samples, with a mean of 0.007 mg/kg having standard deviation of 0.0047, and standard error of 0.0027. This was significantly higher than the control, which had negligible arsenic levels with mean value of 0.0001 mg/kg, standard deviation of 0, and standard error of 0. The concentration of cadmium in sample 2 also recorded the highest level with a mean of 0.0493 mg/kg, standard deviation of 0.111, and standard error of 0.0064, compared to that of the control site having a mean value of 0.0057 mg/kg, the low variability in cadmium concentration detected in sample 2 suggest persistent contamination, likely due to artisanal refining activities. The concentration of mercury remained insignificant in both sample 2 and the control, having mean value of 0.0001 mg/kg, standard deviation of 0, and standard error of 0. The pH in sample 2 has a mean of 6.36, standard deviation of 0.1607, and standard error of 0.0928 which is slightly more acidic than that of the control having a mean value of 6.47, which may enhance the mobility of metals such as arsenic and cadmium, contributing to their higher concentration in the soil sample.

The result in Table 4 shows that Arsenic concentrations were negligible, with a mean of 0.0001 mg/kg, standard deviation of 0, and standard error of 0, which is similar to the control values. Cadmium concentrations in Sample 3 had a mean of 0.0367 mg/kg with standard deviation of 0.0179, and standard error of 0.0131, higher than the control sample with lower values in mean, standard deviation and standard error. High changes in cadmium intensity or accumulation in Sample 3 suggests uneven contamination, possibly due to differences in connection to pollution sources or variations in soil properties. Lead concentrations in Sample

3 were mild, having a mean of 0.3463 mg/kg, standard deviation of 0.0693, and standard error of 0.0400, higher than the control that has mean of 0.0964 mg/kg, standard deviation of 0.0838, and standard error of 0.0484 but lower than lead levels observed in Sample 1.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistic of soil parameters in sample 3.

Parameter	Mean (Sample 3)	Std. Dev. (Sample 3)	Std. Error (Sample 3)	Mean (Control)	Std. Dev. (Control)	Std. Error (Control)
pH	6.35	0.09	0.051961524	6.47	0.115325626	0.066583281
Arsenic	0.0001	0	0	0.0001	0	0
Cadmium	0.036666667	0.017925773	0.013063945	0.005733333	0.00975722	0.006899396
Lead	0.346333333	0.069349357	0.04003887	0.096366667	0.083801571	0.04838286
Mercury	0.0001	0	0	0.0001	0	0

Source: Authors Analysis

The concentration of mercury in the soil remains minimal in both sample 3 and the control having a mean value of 0.0001 mg/kg, standard deviation of 0, standard error of 0. The pH in sample 3 had a mean value of 6.35, standard deviation of 0.09, and standard error of 0.0520 which was slightly lower than the control region which had a mean value of 6.47, showing minimal acidic conditions. This acidity may have also contributed the mobility of cadmium, contributing to its higher but uneven concentration in the sample.

Perception study of the impact of artisanal refining on human health and Environment

Response from respondents on the impact of artisanal refining presented in Table 5. Respondent’s opinion was sought and the level of agreement or disagreement with the questions were measured and recorded.

Table 5. Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents.

Category	Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	28	45.9
Female	33	54.1
Age		
Under 18	2	3.3
18–35	20	32.8
36–50	17	27.9

Above 50	22	36.1
Level of Education		
No formal education	9	14.8
Primary school	14	23.0
Secondary school	25	41.0
Higher education	13	21.3
Occupation		
Farmer	20	32.8
Trader	18	29.5
Artisan	11	18.0
Others	12	19.7
Duration of Residency		
Less than 5 years	3	4.9
5–10 years	9	14.8
Over 10 years	49	80.3

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Figure 2. Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents.
Source: Field Survey.

According to the responses received from respondents in the Oyigba community shown in table 5 and Figure 2, 45.9% of respondents were male and 54.1% were female, which is indicative of the gender distribution of the population with different perspectives and opinions. The majority of respondents were over 50 with 36.1%, followed by those between the ages of 18 and 35 who are 32.8%, indicating that the majority of respondents were vibrant youth who have had a good level of exposure and insight about the activities underway. Another group of respondents with high responses were those between the ages of 36 and 50 and they were 27.9%, indicating that the respondent has gained in-depth knowledge of the refining activities ongoing in the community.

The least number of respondents were under 18 representing 3.3%. more reliable firsthand information gotten from the residents of the Oyigba community due to the experience and exposure to the environment. The response based on the level of education shows that 25 of the respondents attended secondary school, with 41.0% showing that the respondents are enlightened and can detect when something is good or bad. 14 of the respondents went to primary school, indicating 23%, which has at least gotten a background knowledge of formal learning, with 13 of the respondents who have attended higher educational systems showing 21.3% with advanced knowledge, understanding, and exposure to life based on their level of formal learning, which contributes to the reasonable input to the response gotten with 9 of the respondents with no formal education which has the lowest percentage of 14.8%. this shows the respondents' level of literacy and their understanding of the environment's ongoing refinement activities.

Majority of respondents were farmers, as indicated by 20 of them, or 32.8%, who had firsthand knowledge of the impact of this activity on their crops and soil, which has affected food production. In terms of occupation, 29.5% of respondents were traders, 18.0% were artisans who are in charge of locally refining activities in the environment, and 19.7% indicated other occupations and fields of life. According to the respondents' level of community residence, 80.3% of them have been there for more than ten years, giving them accurate information about the local environment. With 4.9% indicating less than five years and 14.8% indicating five to ten years, it provides a thorough record of local environmental knowledge.

Table 6. Environmental Impacts.

Category	Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
Awareness of Refineries		
Yes	61	100.0
No	0	0.0
Observed Soil Changes		
Yes	61	100.0
No	0	0.0
Soil Changes Observed		
Soil discoloration	26	42.6

Reduced fertility	56	91.8
Oil patches or contamination	47	77.0
Unusual odours	51	83.6
Hydrocarbons Affect Soil		
Yes	51	83.6
No	10	16.4
Stunted Crop Growth		
Yes	51	83.6
No	10	16.4

Source: Field Survey (2024).

Figure 3. Graphical representation of Environmental impact
Source: Field Survey

Table 6 and Figure 3 displays the responses of Oyigba community members regarding the environmental impacts of artisanal refining. Based on the above table, 100% of respondents indicated that they were aware of the environmental effects of artisanal refining activities, while none indicated that they were unaware of them. Regarding observed soil changes, 100% of respondents indicated that they were aware of observed soil changes. Based on the observed soil changes, 42.6% of respondents noted soil discoloration, While 91.8% pointed out decreased fertility, 77.0% identified oil stains and contamination, and 83.6% indicated the unusual odor they typically detected as a result of the environmental activities.

Table 7. Health impact Among Residents.

Category	Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
Health problem among residents		
Yes	61	100.0
No	0	0.0
Health Issues Observed		
Respiratory problems	56	91.8
Skin irritations	56	91.8
Eye infections	42	68.9
Fatigue or weakness	40	65.6
Diagnosed Health Conditions		
Yes	38	62.3
No	23	37.7
Health Problems and Refining		
Yes	55	90.2
No	6	9.8
Severity of Health Problems		
Mild	8	13.1
Moderate	27	44.3
Severe	26	42.6
Access to Healthcare		
Yes	29	47.5
No	32	52.5

Source: Field Survey 2024.

Figure 4. Graphical representation of Health impact of Artisanal refining
Source: Field Survey

The survey analysis in Table 7 and Figure 4 shows that 77.26% of respondents on average agreed that artisanal oil refining in the community has a negative impact on their health, indicating that they have been affected directly or indirectly by the current practice. On the other hand, 28.57% of the respondents said they are not impacted by artisanal refining because they do not have any associated health problems. However, the significant percentage of people reporting health problems indicates that this activity has resulted in skin and respiratory problems, which have impacted the majority of inhabitants' general well-being.

Table 8. Impact on agriculture and Vegetation.

Category	Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
Changes in Vegetation		
Yes	61	100.0
No	0	0.0

Observed Vegetation Changes		
Drying or death of plants	58	95.1
Loss of vegetation cover	47	77.0
Reduced crop yield	54	88.5
Pollutants Affect Vegetation		
Yes	61	100.0
No	0	0.0
Crops Affected		
Cassava	40	65.6
Cocoyam	33	54.1
Corn	20	32.8
Palm tree	4	6.6
Mangrove	2	3.3
Yam	2	3.3
Effects of Artisanal Refineries		
Loss of farmland productivity	51	83.6
Health problems	60	98.4
Economic challenges	30	49.2
Reduction in standard of living	1	1.6
Suggested Actions		
Provide alternative livelihoods	47	77.0
Implement stricter regulations	35	57.4
Ban artisanal refineries	20	32.8
Regular environmental clean-up	3	4.9
Overall Impact		
Positive	1	1.6
Neutral	14	23.0
Negative	46	75.4

Source: Field Survey (2024).

Figure 5. Impact of Artisanal refining on Agriculture and Vegetation.
Source: Field Survey.

The result in Table 8 shows that all the respondents 100% confirmed awareness of artisanal refineries and observed changes in the soil and vegetation. The observed impacts on vegetation were much observed, with 95.1% reporting drying or death of plants, 77.0% observing a loss of vegetation cover, and 88.5% indicating reduced crop yields. Also, all 100% of the respondents agreed that pollutants affect vegetation, signifying widespread awareness of environmental degradation caused by artisanal refinery activities.

The crops most affected include cassava having a percentage of 65.6, cocoyam with a percentage of 54.1, and corn with a percentage of 32.8, while less commonly affected crops were palm trees having a percentage of 6.6, mangroves having 3.3%, and yams 3.3%. The findings shows that crops that are crucial for food security and local livelihoods are particularly vulnerable to pollution. The wider effects of artisanal refineries in the environment include an 83.6% loss of farmland productivity as identified by the respondents, health problems reported by 98.4% of respondents, and economic challenges identified by 49.2%. The majority of respondents (75.4%) said that artisanal refining had a negative overall influence on agriculture, while only 1.6% said that their level of life had decreased. To address the issues, 77.0% of respondents suggested the provision of alternative livelihoods, 57.4% requested for the

implementation of stricter environmental regulations, 32.8% of the respondents supported banning artisanal refineries, and 4.9% of the respondents recommended regular environmental clean-up. In respective of these suggestions, only 1.6% of respondents considered the overall impact of these activities to be positive, while 23.0% viewed them as neutral.

4. CONCLUSION

The result from this study highlights the inefficient nature of artisanal refining activities in Oyigba community. Artisanal refining though it has been a means of livelihood for some individuals has caused health issues to a lot of persons including destruction of agricultural crops and soil making land unsuitable for farming, result from the findings highlight high concentration of heavy metals in refining site with a slight acidic soil as a result of refining activities with lead and cadmium having the highest values thereby affecting crop production, contaminating the soil, and affecting both the health of humans and animals in the region. however, the situation in Oyigba community correlate to the happenings in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria where soils has been contaminated due to illegal practices thereby putting many life at risk. The study therefore recommends continues monitoring of vulnerable communities, environmental restoration, public health intervention and sustainable economic practices. Long term effect of artisanal refining activities will affect the source of livelihood and well-being of the communities involved without immediate response.

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